

Authoritarian or Democratic AI?

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For longtime after humans appeared on the Earth, any technology was of only one kind: tools available to small communities, centered and directed by peoples, for having a local, relatively weak impact. Based on human skills, animal energy, remaining under the directive of the user even when employing machines, developed with a discreet use of nature gifts, they had limited horizons of achievement. At the same time, they were based on renewable resources, and hence sustainable. Given their wide diffusion and modest demand, they had great power of adaptation and recuperation. They were the support of every culture developed in history, leaving margins of autonomy and creativity to populations, even when under authoritarian regimes.

Those technologies will be given the attribute of democratic. Here it is assumed, as a spinal principle of democracy, that what is common to all men should be placed above that which any organization, institution or small group may claim for himself, giving a final authority to the whole, rather than the part. To various degrees, democratic societies present self-government, free communication as between equals, access to common knowledge, protection against external controls, and moral responsibility for behavior affecting whole community. At the same time they give autonomy to individuals, to grant the highest degree of self-direction, self-expression, and self-realization.

With the beginning of what can be identified as civilization, as known also today, it starts a new configuration of technical invention, scientific observation, and centralized political control. Diversified activities human-sized, were united on a monumental scale, into a new kind of mass organization. Goals beyond the village horizon could be reached, unifying efforts of once too autonomous men, too decentralized to act voluntarily in unison. Thanks to this cognitive revolution - to scientific discoveries, written record, mathematics, irrigation - new complex human machines were invented, composed by specialized, standardized, replaceable parts.

Mass construction via work, and mass destruction via armies, opened enormous possibilities, exploiting faster resources in home territory, conquering new ones - especially those not developing in the same way - and creating abundance. Immense food crops supported big urban population, but also released part of it for pure scientific, religious, bureaucratic or military activities. It was possible to compensate the unsustainable increase in ecological impact - the possibility of the ecosystems to support life - thanks to technologies of a new kind. To these it will be given the attribute of authoritarian.

Several weaknesses might be part of a system driven by them. Technology availability was initially limited to big urban centers, at least until most of the population was dedicated to agriculture. Coherence of the system was based on irrational beliefs, obedience to power, forced labor or slavery. And finally, its dependence on sometime actively disobedient servo-mechanisms, human enough to have wishes that do not coincide with those of the system.

Getting to today, it might seem that experimental science is the guarantee of a peaceful, productive, democratic, industrial society. Seeming to accept the democratic principle that every member has his goods share, providing food, housing, transportation, communication, medical care, entertainment, education in quantities that were hardly available even for a minority in the past. To one condition, only asking for what the system provides, in quantities that the system, not the person requires.

No less irrationally than before, the same idea that the system itself must expand without limits at whatever cost is still present, with the ends of maximizing energy, speed, and automation, with no regards on the complexity of conditions that sustain life. Danger does not come from any specific discovery or invention, but in this system-centered global society, it is not visible who issues commands. Human limitations are overcome by transforming enormous amount of minerals with the use of fossil energy. Consolidating mass control, the system eliminates human personality, tries to take control over nature, and over man itself.

How Artificial Intelligence would fit in this discourse and which kind of technology would be? It is possible to evaluate a technology by looking at how it will be used, or by investigating what it is needed for such technology to exist?

After multiplying his force with machines, his intelligence with computers, man would delegate his decisions and then his responsibilities to AI. May be forgetting a great lesson of the history: prepare for the unexpected. Only living human beings are an authentic expression of the whole, life cannot be delegated, and its attributes cannot be transferred to a machine or a mechanical collective.